

Deliverable D7.1

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

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1. Executive Summary

The BY-COVID Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy provides plans, guidance, support and resources to maximise the impact of the BY-COVID project. The aim of this document is to act as a reference point for all aspects of BY-COVID communications, exploitation and dissemination activities by providing guidelines to project partners internally, and harmonising communications and messaging to interested external parties.

In this document we present and discuss:

- Stakeholders and key messages
- Communication channels
- Branding and assets
- Public engagement
- Dissemination
- Exploitation

The document is live and will be updated continuously as the project progresses.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities contribute to all project objectives, with the largest impact on engagement deliverable of Objective 1, Key Result 4.

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research.	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Yes
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	Yes
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres.	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	Yes
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	Yes
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants	Yes

	<p>to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.</p> <p>4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern.</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	Yes

<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS).</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p>	Yes
	<p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	Yes

3. Introduction

BeYond-COVID (BY-COVID) aims to provide comprehensive open data on SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious diseases across scientific, medical, public health and policy domains. Running for three years, the project brings together 53 partners from 19 countries. The project will enable scientists across multiple domains, including SMEs and industry, to access data and generate new knowledge on infectious diseases and ultimately improve European preparedness for future pandemics.

This document is an outline of the strategy in place to communicate, disseminate and exploit outputs from the BY-COVID project. The strategy aims to capitalise on the collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of the project by promoting clear, inclusive and targeted communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts.

This deliverable is part of BY-COVID Work Package 7. The Work Package aims to develop and implement the project-wide communications and outreach strategy, ensuring key stakeholders including scientists, industry and SMEs, policy makers and the public have awareness of the project and opportunities to engage, use project outputs and provide feedback to partners.

In order to develop this document we draw upon:

- the experience and skills of the [ELIXIR External Relations team](#)
- lessons learned from the delivery of the [ELIXIR Hub portfolio of projects](#)
- the specific project needs defined by the interaction with different WPs, the coordination team, and project partners
- the public engagement expertise of [Sciensano](#), a research institute and the national public health institute of Belgium

4. Description of work

4.1 Stakeholders and key messages

The main BY-COVID stakeholders are:

- Data generators (e.g. deposition of FAIR data, data management) from the private and public sector
- Data consumers (e.g. data analysis, workflows) from the private and public sector
- Policy-makers and funding organisations
- Infrastructure providers

- National and international consortia and organisations involved in infectious disease research and allied social science research
- COVID-19 and infectious disease medical services and patient groups
- Adults, children and young people at risk of infectious diseases and affected by public health policy decisions

The sectors covered by the BY-COVID project include social sciences, public health, molecular life sciences and medical sciences.

4.1.1 Key messages

The BY-COVID project key messages are:

Objectives

- The BY-COVID project aims to make COVID-19 data accessible to everyone, scientists in laboratories, medical staff in hospitals or government officials
- Going beyond SARS-CoV-2 data, the project will provide a framework for making data from other infectious diseases open and accessible to everyone. It will build bridges between public health, clinical sciences, social sciences and molecular sciences.

Motivation

- The world has generated vast amounts of data in response to the COVID-19 pandemic which comes from many different sources. Identifying, connecting and integrating these data for effective analysis is a challenging yet vital task.

Approach

- Mobilising data - ensuring data from around the world can easily be submitted to core data hubs
- Connecting data - linking infectious disease data e.g. clinical data with viral data
- Standardising data - providing recommended data management best practices and standards for describing data
- Exposing and analysing data - providing data analysis methods and protocols

Outcomes

Making SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious disease data easier to access, aggregate and analyse to:

- Enable scientists in academia and industry to respond faster to new SARS-CoV-2 strains or other pathogens causing infectious diseases

- Help policy-makers assess the impact of COVID-19 and take appropriate measures to protect people
- Facilitate open innovation in academia and industry across disciplines

4.2 Communication channels

4.2.1 Website

The primary communication channel for the BY-COVID project is the dedicated website, found at by-covid.org. This provides comprehensive information about the project, and will be the host for any public engagement activities. The primary goals of the website are:

1. To let people know what the project is, why it was created (goals) and why it is important.
2. To disseminate the project deliverables.
3. To advertise the progress and impact of the project (including news stories).
4. To explain how the project is organised: duration, leadership, governance, who is involved, who is doing what, how the project is run, contact info.

Further information is in the website [strategy document](#).

4.2.1.1 Website content

The ELIXIR Hub External Relations team is part of the BY-COVID Coordination Office (WP7) and has full editorial control over the website content. However, in developing new content, ELIXIR Hub will regularly consult project partners and other relevant groups within the project as well as external stakeholders. All materials to be published on the website should be sent to webmaster@elixir-europe.org.

4.2.1.2 Spelling conventions

The following conventions have been applied to the BY-COVID website as well as to other communication outputs.

- BY-COVID, always capitalised
- Use English [EC style guide](#)

4.2.2 BY-COVID newsletter

The [BY-COVID newsletter](#) for internal and external stakeholders is released quarterly. All content published in the newsletter must be directly related to BY-COVID, some

announcements from third parties will be considered if relevant to the mission and/or activities of the project.

In addition to news and updates from the project, each issue will also feature different BY-COVID consortium partners - presenting the partners' core activities and their roles in the project. The newsletter sign-up form is embedded in the website footer and published back-issues of the newsletter will be available to view. Individuals will be regularly encouraged to sign up for the newsletter wherever BY-COVID is being presented, and through social media. The newsletter will be managed and created via the email marketing platform MailerLite.

While the ELIXIR Hub is responsible for creating and managing the newsletter and the mailing list, the content for the newsletter is developed in consultation with Work Package Leaders. In this context, ELIXIR Hub offers:

- A [registration form](#) for the mailing list for all partners, external stakeholders and interested parties to subscribe to the newsletter.
- Extensive communications coverage to gather new subscribers on social media, mailing lists, [ELIXIR's website](#) and the [BY-COVID website](#).
- Provide a [newsletter archive](#) via the website.
- Create a planning sheet and editorial calendar to programme the newsletter after a key date for the project.

4.2.2.1 Target audience

The newsletter is open to subscription from any individual and the project is focused on a broad demographic of scientists (e.g. biologists, data scientists, social scientists and policy makers). Therefore the content will be understandable and accessible, with information provided to link to further technical details.

4.2.3 Social media

In addition to promoting specific activities of BY-COVID and driving more visitors to the website, the project's social media strategy focuses on community building and networking. The new [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts are named BY-COVID project and are managed and monitored by ELIXIR's Communications Officers within the External Relations team.

4.2.3.1 Tagging

Where appropriate, social media posts should tag partners and/or project groups whose work is being communicated. To ease the process of identifying the accounts for all 53 project partners, a *Communications contacts at BY-COVID project partners* document has

been drafted, accessible to all project partners. In addition, a publicly available [twitter list](#) of all the project accounts involved in BY-COVID has been created.

4.3 Branding

The BY-COVID logo and branding guidelines are publicly available on the BY-COVID website [Outreach and Media](#) page to facilitate the correct usage of the BY-COVID branding.

4.3.1 Logo

The logo presents a distinguishable identity from the ELIXIR branding and makes use of the branding from the COVID-19 Data Platform to reflect the strong links between the two initiatives.

Due to the desire for continuity with the [COVID-19 Data Platform](#) aesthetics, the logo was designed in-house by the ELIXIR External Relations team, rather than using external consultation.

4.3.2 Branding guidelines

To facilitate the ease of use of communication materials designed for BY-COVID, the [BY-COVID branding guidelines](#) are presented in a presentation (powerpoint) format, and are freely available through the website. This enables those who wish to present BY-COVID to easily lift icons, logos, design, funding acknowledgements and so on from the guidelines for use in their own presentations.

Project partners are welcome to reach out to the Communications Officers at the ELIXIR Hub should they require further visual materials or assistance in developing presentations for BY-COVID.

All existing diagrams (in .png and .svg formats) and other communications materials, including slides are accessible on the BY-COVID google drive for project participants to access and use.

[BY-COVID Communication Materials](#)>> (requires access to project repository)

4.3.3 Templates

The ELIXIR Hub provides templates for a range of communication activities and reports in keeping with the Branding Guidelines. All presentations, internal or external should use the template and branding provided. Templates include:

- presentation slides
- documents
- deliverables and milestones

[BY-COVID Templates](#)>> (requires access to project repository)

4.4 Communication assets

4.4.1 Graphics, icons and stock images

As detailed in Section 4.3 the BY-COVID logo and branding guidelines are publicly available on the BY-COVID website [Outreach and Media](#) page to facilitate the correct usage of the BY-COVID branding.

Requests for further materials, and details on their usage can be directed to info@elixir-europe.org.

4.4.2 Boilerplate text

The boilerplate text can be reused in new contexts or applications without any significant changes. Examples of use include websites of the project partners, news and press releases and publications.

Boilerplate text

BeYond-COVID (BY-COVID) aims to provide comprehensive open data on SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious diseases across scientific, medical, public health and policy domains. It will strongly emphasise mobilising raw viral sequences, helping to identify and monitor the spread of SARS-CoV-2 variants. The project will further accelerate access to SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 and linking of patient and research data.

4.5 Communication evaluation

All communications activities are logged in the [BY-COVID evidence spreadsheet](#) which records metrics such as audience type, location and size along with details of the activity performed and the outcomes achieved.

Evaluation of the BY-COVID communications activities will be carried out at regular intervals to analyse the impact of communication through each channel. Monitoring the impact of the communications regularly will enable adjustment of the strategy and individual communications activities to ensure they are fit for purpose. Outputs of the analysis will be shared where appropriate with the BY-COVID project partners.

4.5.1 Communication metrics

The communications metrics will measure the engagement rate, the quality of communications and the reach outside the BY-COVID project. Data collected include:

- Web traffic metrics
- Performance of BY-COVID newsletter provided by MailerLite
 - Subscriber Variation
 - Click Rate
 - Opening rate
 - Benchmark with other comparable newsletters
- Twitter analytics (<https://analytics.twitter.com>)
- LinkedIn analytics

4.6 Public engagement

The public engagement activities within BY-COVID focus on creating content and building tools. The goal of these activities is to inform citizens about issues regarding the use of data in pandemic preparedness and crisis management. The tools will be neutral and promote deliberation and interaction to ensure citizens can express their values and needs and engage in a process of co-creation. All end products will be made freely available through the project website.

4.6.1 Content creation

The content will focus on ethical and societal implications of health data use and reuse in the battle against COVID-19 and other infectious diseases. It will combine insights from the humanities, output from other BY-COVID related activities and play into current trends in the news. The focus will be on short, simple, visual and thought provoking information materials. The content will add to and tie in with more general informational materials created for the [TEHDAS e-consultation platform](#). Specific content will be generated for a pedagogical toolkit to support highschool teachers at all levels of education to make their students more aware of issues related to health data sharing and pandemic preparedness.

4.6.2 Dissemination

Dissemination of the materials will take place through the BY-COVID website, the networks of BY-COVID partners and already existing networks around citizen engagement about health data. A communications toolkit with suggested posts for different platforms will be created to support dissemination activities for every type of content created. The pedagogical toolkit will be disseminated to teachers through online teaching material portals and existing groups on social media.

4.7 Dissemination

Dissemination is the process of ensuring all scientific outputs are openly available, as early as possible and in forms that are easily accessible, understandable and reusable. Dissemination fosters the use and uptake of results and outcomes, in contrast communications covers the sharing and promotion of wider project efforts. Dissemination activities target audiences that are likely to use the results in their own work, for instance peers and experts in and outside of the project, including policy-makers. Communications activities target multiple audiences beyond the project consortium, including the media and the public.

In order to distinguish between the distinct activities of dissemination and communication, the [BY-COVID evidence spreadsheet](#) captures the details of stakeholder and audience involvement along with measures of the outcomes achieved.

4.7.1 Tracking and monitoring

Dissemination efforts are the responsibility of all work packages, in contrast to communications and exploitation efforts which fall primarily under WP7. BY-COVID dissemination efforts are tracked in the [BY-COVID evidence spreadsheet](#). The spreadsheet is part of the WP8 activities, and will be accessible to all BY-COVID partners to fulfil the obligation of informing project partners and giving them the opportunity to comment and contribute.

4.7.2 Publications

Project partners add manuscripts, preprints and peer-reviewed publications to the [BY-COVID evidence spreadsheet](#), which is complemented by text-mining of relevant publishing repositories.

The following sentence is used by project partners to acknowledge project support in research publications: *This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101046203 (BY-COVID).*

4.7.3 Zenodo

A number of [Zenodo](#) communities (one overall community and one community per Work Package) will be created as a home for project outputs such as deliverables, posters and other related documents. Efforts will be made to ensure outputs are published in a timely manner, ensuring good visibility and impact. Dissemination will be facilitated by the use of appropriate metadata when uploading to Zenodo (e.g. grant agreement number 101046203, Horizon Europe, ORCID IDs of the co-authors), which will improve FAIR metadata for discoverability, as well as project-wide aggregation by EC's [OpenAIRE](#). The combined number of views/downloads of project outputs on Zenodo will be used to evaluate project progress.

4.8 Exploitation

Exploitation activities enable the concrete use of research results, either directly by project participants, or indirectly by others outside of the project, including industry. Exploitation of results can be through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes, turning results into value for society. Where dissemination describes and makes results visible to audiences that *may* use the results, exploitation is the *actual* use of the results, during and after the project.

As with communications and dissemination efforts, exploitation efforts are tracked in the [BY-COVID evidence spreadsheet](#) and regularly analysed, reviewed and reported. Examples of exploitation efforts include industry engagement through events and newsletters.

4.9 Visual summary

The combination of communications, dissemination and exploitation efforts recorded in the evidence spreadsheet are used to visualise cross work package activities. Examples of the visualisations produced are shown in Figures 2, 3 and 4 below.

Figure 2

Number of recorded dissemination, exploitation and communication activities over time

Figure 3

Means by which dissemination, exploitation and communication activities in Figure 2 have been carried out

Figure 4

Key stakeholders targeted by some of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities in Figure 2

4.10 Follow-up and project ending

There will be a communications, dissemination and exploitation strategy review meeting six months before the project closes to define a strategy for project ending. This will include ensuring that project outputs remain visible after project channels such as social media are concluded. Relevant content will be migrated to sustainable channels such as the ELIXIR website and the COVID-19 Data Platform and a communications plan will be designed and implemented to inform stakeholders.